

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

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SUPPLEMENTARY TEXT

Text S1. Detailed information for the OGTT and clamp analysis

A 75-g OGTT and hyperinsulinemic-euglycemic clamp test were performed on separate days between 3 and 6 days after the initiation of dapagliflozin treatment. In the standard 75-g OGTT, blood samples were collected before and at 15, 30, 60, 90, and 120 min after glucose ingestion for measurement of the levels of plasma glucose as well as serum insulin, C-peptide reactive protein (CPR), and glucagon. Serum CPR and insulin were measured with chemiluminescent enzyme immunoassays (Lumipulse Presto Insulin; Fujirebio, Tokyo, Japan), and serum glucagon was measured with a sandwich enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (Merckodia AB, Uppsala, Sweden). The plasma glucose concentration was measured using an enzymatic method with hexokinase G-6-PDH kit (Shino-Test Corporation, Tokyo, Japan). Total urinary glucose excretion over 120 min was also measured during the OGTT.

The hyperinsulinemic-euglycemic clamp was performed with the use of an artificial endocrine pancreas (STG-55; Nikkiso, Tokyo, Japan) as described previously (1). In brief, a 120-min hyperinsulinemic-euglycemic clamp was initiated by intravenous infusion of human regular insulin (Humulin R, Eli Lilly Japan K.K.) at a rate of $40 \text{ mU m}^{-2} \text{ min}^{-1}$ and the hyperinsulinemic state was maintained to achieve a target glucose level (the fasting glucose level of each individual) and a serum insulin concentration of $100 \text{ }\mu\text{U/ml}$. Plasma glucose concentration was measured every minute during the clamp and averaged over a 5-min period. Blood was collected from arterialized veins, which were confirmed by measurement of oxygen saturation. Plasma glucose as well as serum insulin, CPR, and glucagon were measured before and at 30, 60, 90, and 120 min after the onset of insulin infusion as described for the OGTT. Total urinary glucose excretion over 120 min was also measured during the clamp test.

A total of 87 subjects was initially included in the study. After exclusion of patients with hepatic dysfunction ($n = 1$) or renal dysfunction ($n = 2$) as well as of those with missing OGTT or clamp data ($n = 12$) and those who had undergone pancreatectomy ($n = 4$), data from 68 subjects were analyzed (Figure S1).

Text S2. Detailed information for mathematical models

We constructed the mathematical model of the feedback loop that links glucose and insulin (GI model) by modifying our previously reported model² with the addition of flux 8 as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{dGc}{dt} &= \text{flux 1} - \text{flux 2} + \text{flux 3} - \text{flux 4} - \text{flux 8} + \text{influx } Gc \\
&= k_1Y - k_2Gc + \frac{k_3}{k_9 + I} - k_4GcI - k_8Gc + f_1(t) \\
\frac{dI}{dt} &= \text{flux 6} - \text{flux 7} + \text{influx } I = k_6X - k_7I + f_2(t) \\
\frac{dY}{dt} &= -\text{flux 1} + \text{flux 2} = -k_1Y + k_2Gc \\
\frac{dX}{dt} &= \text{flux 5} - \text{flux 6} = k_5Y - k_6X
\end{aligned}$$

where the variables Gc and I denote blood glucose and insulin concentrations, respectively. In this model, flux 1 represents the systemic circulation of glucose from the pancreas or of infused glucose to target organs, whereas flux 2 corresponds to the circulation of glucose to the pancreas. Both flux 3 and flux 4 are related to insulin sensitivity; flux 3 is inhibited by I and corresponds to glucose production whereas flux 4 depends on both Gc and I and corresponds to glucose uptake. Flux 5 and flux 6 are related to insulin secretion; flux 5 depends on Y and corresponds to insulin secretion whereas flux 6 depends on X and corresponds to systemic circulation of insulin from the pancreas to target organs. Flux 7 depends on I and corresponds to insulin clearance. Flux 8 depends on Gc and corresponds to urinary glucose. Of note, during the glucose clamp test, blood glucose levels are maintained at approximately 100 mg/dl, which is significantly lower than the urinary glucose excretion threshold under normal physiological conditions. Therefore, we considered the urinary glucose excretion in individuals who do not take SGLT2 inhibitors to be zero. Influx Gc and influx I correspond to infused glucose and insulin during the hyperinsulinemic-euglycemic clamp, respectively.

The actual glucose infusion rate (GcIR, $\text{mg kg}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$) and insulin infusion rate (IIR, $\text{mU kg}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$) were converted to the corresponding blood concentrations (cGcIR and cIIR, respectively) as previously described (2):

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{cGcIR (mg dL}^{-1}\text{min}^{-1}) &= 100 \frac{\text{GcIR (mg kg}^{-1}\text{min}^{-1}) \cdot \text{BW}}{\text{BW} \cdot \text{BV}} \\
\text{cIIR (\mu U mL}^{-1}\text{min}^{-1}) &= 1000 \frac{\text{IIR (mU kg}^{-1}\text{min}^{-1}) \cdot \text{BW}}{\text{BW} \cdot \text{BV}}
\end{aligned}$$

where BW denotes body weight and BV denotes blood volume (75 and 65 mL/kg for men and women, respectively).

The fluxes Gc and I denote glucose and insulin infusions, respectively. These fluxes follow the nonlinear functions $f_1(t)$ and $f_2(t)$ that predict glucose and insulin infusion concentrations, respectively, and are given by the following equations:

$$f_1(t) = gi_1 \frac{(t/gi_3)^{gi_2}}{1+(t/gi_3)^{gi_2}} \quad f_2(t) = ii_1 \exp(ii_2 t) + ii_3$$

The parameters gi_j and ii_j ($j = 1, 2, 3$) were estimated to reproduce infusion rates for each subject with a nonlinear least squares technique (3).

We also constructed a mathematical model of the feedback loop that links glucose, insulin, and glucagon (GIG model) as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dGc}{dt} &= \text{flux GN} - \text{flux GU} - \text{flux U} + \text{influx } Gc \\ &= \frac{k_{GN}Gg}{(k_{GN_I} + I)(k_{GN_{Gg}} + Gg)} - k_{GU}Gc \frac{I}{k_{GU_I} + I} - k_u Gc + f_1(t) \\ \frac{dI}{dt} &= k_{ratio} \text{flux IS} - \text{flux IC} + \text{influx } I = k_{ratio} \frac{k_{IS}GcGg}{(k_{IS_{Gc}} + Gc)(k_{IS_{Gg}} + Gg)} - k_{IC}I + f_2(t) \\ \frac{dGg}{dt} &= \text{flux GgS} - \text{flux GgC} = \frac{k_{GgS}}{(k_{GgS_I} + I)(k_{GgS_{Gc}} + Gc)} - k_{GgC}Gg \\ \frac{dCP}{dt} &= \text{flux IS} - \text{flux CPC} = \frac{k_{IS}GcGg}{(k_{IS_{Gc}} + Gc)(k_{IS_{Gg}} + Gg)} - k_{CPC}CP \end{aligned}$$

where the variables Gc , I , Gg , and CP denote blood glucose, insulin, glucagon, and C-peptide concentrations, respectively. The functions $f_1(t)$ and $f_2(t)$ are the same as those estimated in the GI model. We converted the units of insulin and C-peptide according to a previous study (4). We also considered reduced models (Table S2) in which the effects of either Gc , I , or Gg were removed from flux GN, flux U, flux GU, flux IS, and flux GgS.

Text S3. Definition of PI_{cle}

As glucagon sensitivity (Gg_{sen}), the extent to which blood glucose concentration is affected by glucagon, increases, blood glucose levels would be expected to increase even in the presence of a high blood concentration of insulin and high insulin sensitivity. Gg_{sen} was therefore defined as follows:

$$Gg_{sen} = \frac{G_0 I_0 f_g}{G_{ss} I_{ss}}$$

where G_0 , I_0 , G_{ss} , I_{ss} , and f_g indicate blood glucose and insulin levels in the fasting state, blood glucose and insulin levels at the steady state, and infused glucose at the steady state during the hyperinsulinemic-euglycemic clamp, respectively. Note that $f_g/G_{ss}I_{ss}$ corresponds to the insulin sensitivity index (ISI) (5).

As glucagon secretion relative to glucagon clearance ($Gg_{sec/cle}$) increases, the blood glucagon-insulin ratio would be expected to increase. $Gg_{sec/cle}$ was thus defined as follows:

$$Gg_{sec/cle} = \frac{Gg_0}{I_0}$$

where Gg_0 and I_0 indicate blood glucagon and insulin levels in the fasting state, respectively. PI_{cle} , the overall effect of glucagon on blood glucose levels, was defined as the product of Gg_{sen} and $Gg_{sec/cle}$, which can be written as follows:

$$PI_{cle} = Gg_{sen}Gg_{sec/cle} = \frac{Gg_0G_0f_g}{G_{ss}I_{ss}}$$

Text S4. Mathematical model of the feedback loop that links glucose, insulin and glucagon (GIG model)

In the GIG model (Figure S3), flux GN depends on Gg and I and corresponds to gluconeogenesis and EGP. Flux GU depends on Gc and I and corresponds to glucose uptake. Flux U depends on Gc and corresponds to urinary glucose excretion. Of note, flux U is the same as flux 8 in the GI model (Figure 1A). Flux IS depends on Gc and Gg and corresponds to insulin secretion. Flux IC depends on I and corresponds to insulin clearance. Flux GgS depends on I and Gc and corresponds to glucagon secretion. Flux GgC depends on Gg and corresponds to glucagon clearance. Flux CPC depends on CP and corresponds to C-peptide clearance.

For each of the 68 patients with type 2 diabetes who are treated with the SGLT2 inhibitor, we estimated the parameters of the model to reproduce the time course of blood glucose, insulin, glucagon, and C-peptide in the hyperinsulinemic-euglycemic clamp with the same method as adopted in Figure 1B. Figure S3B shows the simulated and measured data for the same subject shown in Figure 1B.

To confirm that the simulation adequately reflects the characteristics of the study subjects, we evaluated the consistency between ISI calculated from the actual measurements and that calculated from the simulation data. The coefficient of determination (R^2) between

measured ISI and simulated ISI was 0.55 (Figure S3C), suggesting that the model was able to capture the essential characteristics of the time series data.

Estimated parameters related to blood glucose, insulin, and glucagon concentrations in the GIG model are shown in Figure S4A. Some parameters, such as k_{GN} , showed a tendency to diverge (that is, their values reached the predetermined upper limit in some subjects). For subjects with large k_{GN} and k_{GN_I} values, insulin would be expected to have little effect on flux GN, and the time course might be reproduced by a model without the effect of insulin on flux GN, which we denote as “GN_I-” (Figure S4B). In the same manner, for inference of the effects of glucose, insulin, and glucagon in simulation of blood glucose level in each subject, we evaluated the reduced models shown in Table S2. In these models, the effects of either glucose, insulin, or glucagon were removed from flux GN, flux GU, flux IS, and flux GgS.

Text S5. Comparison of models based on the Akaike information criterion (AIC)

We evaluated the reduced models for each subject according to the Akaike information criterion (AIC) (6) (Table S3). The parameters of the models from which the effect of glucose on flux GU was removed did not converge, and so the AIC for those models could not be evaluated. The model with the lowest mean AIC was that designated GN_I-_GU_I-_IS_Gc-_GgS_I-, in which the effects of insulin on flux GN, insulin on flux GU, glucose on flux IS, and insulin on flux GgS were removed (Table S3). This model was also optimal with regard to the greatest number of subjects. The 13 models with the highest mean AIC all shared removal of the effect of glucagon on flux GN. These results suggest that gluconeogenesis (flux GN), glucose uptake (flux GU), insulin secretion (flux IS), and glucagon secretion (flux GgS) can be simulated by glucagon, glucose, glucagon, and glucose, respectively, in patients with type 2 diabetes who are treated with an SGLT2 inhibitor.

The best mathematical model varied from subject to subject (Table S3), which may be related to the results of a previous study showing that interindividual heterogeneity in SGLT2 expression and regulation contributes to interindividual variation in the response to SGLT2 inhibitor treatment (7). We investigated only 68 subjects treated with an SGLT2 inhibitor and 120 subjects without such treatment, and only the former subjects were adopted for development of the GI and GIG models. Further studies with larger and more diverse populations will be required to clarify the effects of SGLT2 inhibitors in patients with type 2 diabetes.

SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURES

FIGURE S1 Flow diagram of participant recruitment

FIGURE S2 Relation between blood glucagon and glucose levels during an oral glucose tolerance test. Scatter plots for log PG120 versus log IRG0 (left), log IRG120 (middle), or log IRG_AUC (right) are shown. Each point corresponds to the values for a single subject in the present cohort. r is Spearman's correlation coefficient, and the P values are for testing the hypothesis of no correlation. PG120, plasma glucose concentration at 120 min during the test; IRG0 and IRG120, immunoreactive glucagon concentration at 0 and 120 min, respectively, during the test; IRG_AUC, area under the curve of immunoreactive glucagon concentration during the test.

FIGURE S3 Mathematical model of the feedback loop that links glucose, insulin, and glucagon (GIG model). (A) Model diagram. The letters in the circles indicate variables of the model, the arrows indicate fluxes, and the lines ending in circles or bars indicate activation and inactivation, respectively. ϕ indicates a fixed value. The variables Gc , I , Gg , and CP represent blood glucose, insulin, glucagon, and C-peptide concentrations, respectively. The variable k_{ratio} represents the fraction of insulin delivered to the peripheral circulation and corresponds to $(1 - \text{hepatic insulin clearance})$. Functions $f_1(t)$ and $f_2(t)$ are described in Text S2. (B) Time courses of blood glucose, insulin, glucagon, and C-peptide concentrations as well as infusion rates of glucose and insulin during a hyperinsulinemic-euglycemic clamp for subject #5 of the present cohort. Blue lines indicate the temporal pattern of simulations, and red circles indicate the time course data of experiments. Simulated values of each variable were rescaled to absolute concentration and plotted. (C) Scatter plot for simulated versus measured insulin sensitivity index (ISI). Each point corresponds to the values for a single subject of the present cohort. R^2 is the coefficient of determination.

FIGURE S4 Estimated parameters in the GIG model and a reduced model. (A) Estimated parameters in the GIG model. The base of the logarithm is 10. (B) In the full model, flux GN was dependent on Gg and I . In the GN_I- model, flux GN was dependent only on Gg .

FIGURE S5 Relations among estimated glucagon-related parameters, PI_{cle} , and blood glucose concentration. (A) Scatter plot for $\log Gg_{sen}Gg_{sec/cle}$ versus $\log k_{GN}k_{GGS}/k_{GGC}^2$. Gg_{sen} and $Gg_{sec/cle}$ correspond to glucagon sensitivity and to glucagon secretion relative to glucagon clearance, respectively (Text S3). The indices k_{GN} , k_{GGS} , and k_{GGC} were calculated by the model designated GN_I-GU_I-IS_Gc-GgS_I- (Table S2), which was optimal for the greatest number of subjects (Table S3), and they conceptually correspond to glucagon sensitivity, glucagon secretion, and glucagon clearance, respectively. Each point

corresponds to the values for a single subject in the present cohort. r is Spearman's correlation coefficient, and the P value is for testing the hypothesis of no correlation. (B) Scatter plot for $\log k_{GN}k_{GGS}/k_{GGC}^2$ versus \log PG120, where PG120 is the plasma glucose concentration at 120 min during an oral glucose tolerance test. (C) Scatter plot for $\log Gg_{sen}Gg_{sec/cle}$ versus $\log k_{GN}k_{GGS}/k_{GGC}$. (D) Scatter plot for $\log k_{GN}k_{GGS}/k_{GGC}$ versus \log PG120. (E) Scatter plot for $\log Gg_{sen}Gg_{sec/cle}$ versus $\log k_{GN}k_{GGS}/k_{GGC}^3$. (F) Scatter plot for $\log k_{GN}k_{GGS}/k_{GGC}^3$ versus \log PG120.

FIGURE S6 Scatter plot for the half-life of insulin calculated using GI model and that calculated using GIG model. r is Spearman's correlation coefficient, and the P value is for testing the hypothesis of no correlation.

SUPPLEMENTARY TABLES

TABLE S1. Exclusion criteria for study entry

Exclusion criteria

1. Severe heart, liver, or renal disease
2. Type 1 diabetes or other type (not type 2 diabetes) of diabetes
3. Use of basal insulin or long-acting glucagon-like peptide-1 (GLP-1) receptor agonist
4. Rash induced by hypoglycemic agent or insulin
5. Recent hypoglycemic event
6. Contraindication for dapagliflozin administration
7. Cognitive disorder or mental illness
8. Pregnancy or breastfeeding
9. Judged inappropriate by researchers

TABLE S2 Reduced models

Model	GN		GU		IS		GgS	
	I	Gg	Gc	I	Gc	Gg	Gc	I
Full model								
GN_I-	-							
GN_Gg-		-						
GU_I-				-				
IS_Gc-					-			
IS_Gg-						-		
GgS_Gc-							-	
GgS_I-								-
GN_I-_GU_I-	-			-				
GN_I-_IS_Gc-	-				-			
GN_I-_IS_Gg-	-					-		
GN_I-_GgS_Gc-	-						-	
GN_I-_GgS_I-	-							-
GN_Gg-_GU_I-		-		-				
GN_Gg-_IS_Gc-		-			-			
GN_Gg-_IS_Gg-		-				-		
GN_Gg-_GgS_Gc-		-					-	
GN_Gg-_GgS_I-		-						-
GU_I-_IS_Gc-				-	-			
GU_I-_IS_Gg-				-		-		
GU_I-_GgS_Gc-				-			-	
GU_I-_GgS_I-				-				-
IS_Gc-_GgS_Gc-					-		-	
IS_Gc-_GgS_I-					-			-
IS_Gg-_GgS_Gc-						-	-	
IS_Gg-_GgS_I-						-		-
GN_I-_GU_I-_IS_Gc-	-			-	-			
GN_I-_GU_I-_IS_Gg-	-			-		-		
GN_I-_GU_I-_GgS_Gc-	-			-			-	
GN_I-_GU_I-_GgS_I-	-			-				-
GN_I-_IS_Gc-_GgS_Gc-	-				-		-	
GN_I-_IS_Gc-_GgS_I-	-				-			-
GN_I-_IS_Gg-_GgS_Gc-	-					-	-	
GN_I-_IS_Gg-_GgS_I-	-					-		-
GN_Gg-_GU_I-_IS_Gc-		-		-	-			
GN_Gg-_GU_I-_IS_Gg-		-		-		-		
GN_Gg-_GU_I-_GgS_Gc-		-		-			-	
GN_Gg-_GU_I-_GgS_I-		-		-				-
GN_Gg-_IS_Gc-_GgS_Gc-		-			-		-	
GN_Gg-_IS_Gc-_GgS_I-		-			-			-
GN_Gg-_IS_Gg-_GgS_Gc-		-				-	-	
GN_Gg-_IS_Gg-_GgS_I-		-				-		-
GU_I-_IS_Gc-_GgS_Gc-				-	-		-	
GU_I-_IS_Gc-_GgS_I-				-	-			-
GU_I-_IS_Gg-_GgS_Gc-				-		-	-	
GU_I-_IS_Gg-_GgS_I-				-		-		-
GN_I-_GU_I-_IS_Gc-_GgS_Gc-	-			-	-		-	
GN_I-_GU_I-_IS_Gc-_GgS_I-	-			-	-			-
GN_I-_GU_I-_IS_Gg-_GgS_Gc-	-			-		-	-	
GN_I-_GU_I-_IS_Gg-_GgS_I-	-			-		-		-
GN_Gg-_GU_I-_IS_Gc-_GgS_Gc-	-			-	-		-	
GN_Gg-_GU_I-_IS_Gc-_GgS_I-	-			-	-			-
GN_Gg-_GU_I-_IS_Gg-_GgS_Gc-	-			-		-	-	
GN_Gg-_GU_I-_IS_Gg-_GgS_I-	-			-		-		-

The variables G_c , I , and G_g represent blood glucose, insulin, and glucagon concentrations, respectively. G_N , G_U , I_S , and G_gS represent gluconeogenesis, glucose uptake, insulin secretion, and glucagon secretion, respectively. The minus symbol ($-$) indicates that the corresponding item was removed. The full model is the same as the model shown in Figure S3A.

TABLE S3 Comparison of models based on the Akaike information criterion (AIC)

Model	AIC mean	No. of subjects for minimum AIC
GN_I- GU_I- IS_Gc- GgS_I-	6.42	11
GN_I- GU_I- IS_Gc- GgS_Gc-	7.98	8
GN_I- GU_I- IS_Gc-	8.33	5
GU_I- GgS_I-	11.03	1
GN_I- GgS_I-	11.59	4
GgS_I-	12.62	0
GN_I- GU_I- GgS_Gc-	13.20	2
GU_I- GgS_Gc-	13.50	2
GN_I-	13.70	0
GN_I- GU_I- GgS_I-	14.23	4
Full model	14.29	4
GN_I- GU_I- IS_Gg- GgS_I-	14.38	6
GN_I- IS_Gc-	16.02	0
GN_I- GU_I- IS_Gg- GgS_Gc-	16.32	3
GN_I- IS_Gc- GgS_I-	16.60	3
IS_Gc-	17.34	0
GgS_Gc-	17.41	0
GN_I- GU_I- IS_Gg-	17.48	0
GU_I- IS_Gg- GgS_I-	17.55	0
GN_I- IS_Gg- GgS_I-	19.10	1
GU_I- IS_Gc- GgS_I-	19.13	2
GU_I-	19.41	0
GN_I- IS_Gc- GgS_Gc-	20.16	3
GU_I- IS_Gc- GgS_Gc-	20.28	1
GN_I- IS_Gg- GgS_Gc-	20.98	0
IS_Gc- GgS_I-	21.32	1
GU_I- IS_Gg- GgS_Gc-	21.67	0
GN_I- GgS_Gc-	22.12	2
GN_I- GU_I-	22.22	0
IS_Gc- GgS_Gc-	22.85	0
GU_I- IS_Gc-	23.01	0
GN_I- IS_Gg-	23.14	0
GU_I- IS_Gg-	23.78	0
GN_Gg- GU_I- IS_Gc- GgS_Gc-	24.32	0
IS_Gg- GgS_I-	26.61	0
GN_Gg- GU_I- IS_Gc- GgS_I-	26.67	3
GN_Gg- GU_I- IS_Gc-	27.80	0
IS_Gg- GgS_Gc-	28.74	0
GN_Gg- GU_I- GgS_Gc-	29.70	0
GN_Gg- GU_I- GgS_I-	30.87	0
IS_Gg-	30.96	1
GN_Gg- IS_Gc- GgS_I-	31.11	0
GN_Gg-	31.22	0
GN_Gg- IS_Gc- GgS_Gc-	31.97	0
GN_Gg- GU_I- IS_Gg- GgS_I-	32.12	0
GN_Gg- GU_I- IS_Gg- GgS_Gc-	32.83	1
GN_Gg- IS_Gg- GgS_I-	34.97	0
GN_Gg- GgS_Gc-	35.52	0
GN_Gg- GgS_I-	35.75	0
GN_Gg- IS_Gg- GgS_Gc-	36.09	0
GN_Gg- GU_I- IS_Gg-	36.14	0
GN_Gg- GU_I-	38.40	0
GN_Gg- IS_Gg-	39.95	0
GN_Gg- IS_Gc-	41.61	0

The number of subjects optimal for each model with the minimum AIC, and the mean value of AIC for each model, are shown.

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